

Can Inflammatory Markers Measured before Total Knee Replacement be an Early Indicator of Revision?

Total Diz Protezi Öncesi Ölçülen İnflamatuar Belirteçler Revizyonun Erken Belirteci Olabilir Mi ?

Ömer Bozduman¹, Ömer Cahit Çıtır²

¹Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology, Samsun University, Samsun, Turkey

²Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology, Şırnak Şehit Aydoğan Aydın State Hospital, Şırnak, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Aim: Knee replacement is one of the most commonly performed orthopedic surgeries today. Various prognostic markers are being investigated to reduce the revision rate. In this study, inflammatory markers measured from preoperative blood were evaluated in terms of revision.

Material and Method: 100 patients who underwent Total Knee prosthesis between January 2017 and December 2021 (50 revisions and 50 non-revisions) were included in the study. Systemic immune-inflammatory index (SII), neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio(NLR), lymphocyte-monocyte ratio(LMR) and platelet-lymphocyte ratios(PLR) calculated from the hemograms taken before the first surgery of these patients; were evaluated comparatively between those with and without revision surgery.

Results: The mean age of the patients was 63.98±9.30 (38-80) in patients who underwent revision, and 65.64±9.45 (46-87) in patients who did not undergo revision. There was no significant difference in age and gender distribution between the revised and non-revised groups (p>0.05). No significant difference was observed in the number of neutrophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes between the revised and non-revised groups (p>0.05). There was no significant difference in SII, NLR, LMR and PLR values between the revised and non-revised groups (p>0.05)

Conclusion: SII, NLR, LMR and PLR calculated from the preoperative hemogram taken before total prosthesis surgery, and no significant relationship was found between revision of the knee prosthesis.

Keywords: total knee arthroplasty, Systemic immune-inflammatory index, revision, neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio

ÖZ

Amaç: Diz protezi günümüzde en sık uygulanan ortopedik ameliyatlardan biridir. Revizyona gitme oranını düşürmek için çeşitli prognostik belirteçler araştırılmaktadır. Bu çalışmada da ameliyat öncesi alınan kanlardan ölçülen inflammatuar belirteçlerin revizyona gitme açısından değerlendirilmesi yapılmıştır.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Çalışmaya Ocak 2017-Aralık 2021 tarihleri arasında Total Diz protezi yapılan 100 hasta(50 revizyona giden 50 revizyona gitmeyen) dahil edilmiştir. Bu hastaların ilk ameliyatları öncesi alınan hemogramlarından hesaplanan Sistemik immün-inflamatuar indeks (SII), nötrofil lenfosit oranı(NLR), lenfosit monosit oranı(LMR) ve platelet lenfosit oranları (PLR); revizyon ameliyatı olan ve olmayanlar arasında karşılaştırmalı olarak değerlendirilmiştir.

Bulgular: Hastaların yaş ortalaması revizyon yapılan hastalarda 63,98±9.30(38-80), revizyon yapılmayan hastalarda ise 65,64±9.45(46-87) olarak bulundu. Revizyon yapılan ve yapılmayan grup arasında yaş ve cinsiyet dağılımı anlamlı farklılık gözlenmedi(p>0.05). Revizyon yapılan ve yapılmayan grup arasında nötrofil, lenfosit, monosit sayısında anlamlı farklılık gözlenmedi(p>0.05). Revizyon yapılan ve yapılmayan grup arasında SII, NLR, LMR ve PLR değerlerinde anlamlı farklılık gözlenmedi(p>0.05)

Sonuç: Total protez ameliyatı öncesi alınan preop hemogramdan hesaplanan Sistemik immün-inflamatuar indeks (SII), nötrofil lenfosit oranı, lenfosit monosit oranı ve platelet lenfosit oranı ile diz protezinin revizyona gitmesi arasında anlamlı bir ilişki bulunamamıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: total diz artroplastisi, Sistemik immün-inflamatuar indeks, revizyon, nötrofil-lenfosit oranı

Corresponding Author: Ömer Bozduman

Address: Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology, Samsun University, Samsun

E-mail: omerbozduman@gmail.com

Başvuru Tarihi/Received: 08.12.2022

Kabul Tarihi/Accepted: 26.12.2022

INTRODUCTION

The knee joint is the largest joint of the human body and has complex movements. The joint most affected by degenerative diseases like osteoarthritis is the knee. Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most common disease of the musculoskeletal system (2). OA; It is a complex disease that causes degeneration of joint components through a combination of structural, mechanical and biological pathways (3). There are many factors in the etiology, and it is the result of the interaction of systemic and local factors (4,5).

The history of total knee arthroplasty, which has been successfully applied for many years in the treatment of knee joint osteoarthritis (gonarthrosis), dates back to the middle of the 19th century. In addition to clinical and functional positive results, loosening due to long years of use of the prosthesis is an absolute result. The need for revision knee arthroplasty arises as a result of the instability that develops due to the decrease in the adhesion between the bone and the prosthesis (6). There are many factors in the loosening of knee arthroplasty components. Overuse, obesity, implant design, surgical technique and infection are some of these factors (6). Miller et al. reported that the first step of the mechanism that causes prosthesis loosening is micro-movements between the prosthesis and bone (7). Other mechanisms are osteolysis, component collapse, inflammatory response to microparticles formed as a result of polyethylene insert abrasion, and inflammation that develops in infective conditions (7). The basic mechanism underlying osteolysis, which is the first condition for the development of non-septic loosening, is the biological response to microparticles formed as a result of prosthesis wear. As a result of phagocytosis of these particles in the joint by macrophages, it initiates the inflammatory process. It has been shown that mediators such as IL-1, IL-6, TNF, PGE2 and metalloproteinase are secreted in the inflammatory process (9-11).

It has been shown that inflammation markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP), IL-6 and TNF- α , which are widely used, are significant in the prognosis of OA and the level of pain due to arthrosis (12,13). On the other hand, parameters such as systemic immune-inflammatory index (SII), neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio, lymphocyte-monocyte ratio and platelet-lymphocyte ratio are practical and innovative biomarkers that are developing in cancer and inflammatory diseases (14).

In this study, we aimed to examine whether the Systemic immune-inflammatory index (SII), neutrophil lymphocyte ratio, lymphocyte monocyte ratio and platelet lymphocyte ratio measured before knee replacement surgery can be used as a prognostic marker for revision.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study was approved by the local ethics committee and complies with the Helsinki Declaration. The informed consent was waived due to the retrospective nature of the study and the assessment utilized anonymous research findings.

In this study, the data of 164 patients who applied to the Orthopedics and Traumatology outpatient clinic with the complaint of pain between January 2017 and December 2021 were retrospectively analyzed. 42 patients who were found to have septic loosening as a result of the examinations were excluded from the study.

Twenty-two patients with known autoimmune disease, acute and chronic infectious disease, systemic inflammatory disease, current immunosuppressive drug use, anti-inflammatory drug use in the last 15 days, chronic liver disease, history of malignancy, and disease causing coagulation disorder were excluded. As a result of physical examination and imaging, 50 patients who were diagnosed with aseptic loosening in knee prosthesis, underwent revision total knee arthroplasty and had at least 1 year of regular follow-up were selected. Fifty patients undergoing total knee arthroplasty and not undergoing revision knee arthroplasty were selected as the control group. As a result, a total of 100 patients were included in the study. It was observed that total knee prosthesis was applied in various brands and models in line with the physician's preference in the patients. All of the patients were selected from those who had a total knee prosthesis that PCL-Substituting Knee Prosthesis

Neutrophil, lymphocyte, platelet and monocyte values obtained from CBC tests performed within 10 days before surgery in the included patients were used. Systemic Inflammatory Index (SII) (Neutrophil *Platelet/Lymphocyte), Neutrophil-Lymphocyte ratio (NLR), Lymphocyte-Monocyte ratio (LMR) and Platelet-Lymphocyte ratio (PLR) parameters were calculated.

Statistical analysis

IBM SPSS version 26.0 software program (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) was used for statistical analysis. Mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values were used in the descriptive statistics of the data. The distribution of variables was measured with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Mann-Whitney U test and independent sample test were used in the analysis of quantitative independent data. Chi-square test was used in the analysis of qualitative independent data, and Fischer test was used when the chi-square test conditions were not met. A P value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study included 100 patients, 50 revisions (41 Female, 9 Male) and 50 non-revision (41 Female, 9 Male) patients between 2017-2021.

The mean age of the patients was 63.98 ± 9.30 (38-80) in patients who underwent revision, and 65.64 ± 9.45 (46-87) in patients who did not undergo revision.

There was no significant difference in age and gender distribution between the revised and non-revised groups ($p > 0.05$).

No significant difference was observed in the number of neutrophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes between the revised and non-revised groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in SII, NLR, LMR and PLR values between the revised and non-revised groups ($p > 0.05$) (**Table 1**).

DISCUSSION

A hemogram is a laboratory evaluation performed before almost all surgeries. It is frequently used for many evaluations because it is both cheap and easy to access (14). It has been shown in many studies that there is a correlation between the proportional relationship between the blood markers in the hemogram and the prognosis of some diseases (15-18). No relationship was found between the indicators and revision.

Recent studies have shown that the SII value calculated by peripheral lymphocyte, neutrophil and platelet counts is a good index for demonstrating local immune response and systemic inflammation. SII is an index of inflammation that is easy to calculate and can be reproduced from CBC results. It has been found to be significant in the prediction of prognosis and in patient follow-up in conditions such as various malignancies (hepatocellular cancer, esophageal cancer, small cell

lung cancer), cardiogenic shock, adult Still's disease, ankylosing spondylitis (15-20).

Although there are many studies on the cancer prognosis of emerging and innovative biomarkers with parameters such as systemic immune-inflammatory index (SII), neutrophil lymphocyte ratio, lymphocyte monocyte ratio and platelet lymphocyte ratio (14), no significant difference was observed in our study in terms of the prognosis of total knee prosthesis ($p > 0.05$).

It has been found that these parameters, which have significant results as inflammatory markers in many malignant and inflammatory diseases, do not give significant results as early markers of knee replacement revision. This may be because the inflammation that develops in aseptic knee arthroplasty is not at a level to affect systemic blood parameters. Also, the small number of patients in the study may have affected the statistical analysis. In addition, patients with autoimmune diseases, a history of acute and chronic infections, systemic inflammatory diseases, a history of malignancy and coagulation disorders were not included in the study. However, a similar trial was conducted in this group of patients and it was likely that a statistically significant change in the parameters studied could be detected.

Our study had several limitations. Our study included only a limited number of patients and is single centered. Future multicenter studies with higher patient numbers will provide more accurate information.

CONCLUSION

No significant correlation was found between the Systemic immune-inflammatory index (SII), neutrophil lymphocyte ratio, lymphocyte monocyte ratio and platelet lymphocyte ratio calculated from the preop hemogram taken before the total prosthesis surgery and revision of the knee prosthesis.

Table 1. Relationship with demographic data and hematological parameters of patients

Descriptive Statistics							
	Revised			Non-revised			p
	Mean±SD	Minimum	Maximum	Mean±SD	Minimum	Maximum	
NEU	4,50±1.8	2,31	10,86	4,87±2.13	1,90	12,90	0,23
LYM	2,01±0.73	0,70	3,84	2,19±0.77	0,50	4,30	0,19
MONO	0,47±0.17	0,02	0,93	0,48±0.18	0,20	1,30	0,7
SII	732,50±629.91	257,83	3173,63	687,01±553.02	163,00	3168,00	0,98
NLR	2,62±1.98	1,17	11,63	2,90±3.58	0,98	24,00	0,63
LMR	8,01±26.58	1,20	192,00	4,90±1.91	1,08	10,75	0,13
PLR	156,47±89.55	61,39	590,14	133,61±48.93	66,25	271,33	0,29
AGE	63,98±9.30	38	80	65,64±9.45	46	87	0,55
Gender		Female 41 Male 9			Female 41 Male 9		1.00

ETHICAL DECLARATIONS

Ethics Committee Approval: This study was approved by the local ethics committee and complies with the Helsinki Declaration.

Informed Consent: Because the study was designed retrospectively, no written informed consent form was obtained from patients.

Referee Evaluation Process: Externally peer-reviewed.

Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Financial Disclosure: The authors declared that this study has received no financial support.

Author Contributions: All of the authors declare that they have all participated in the design, execution, and analysis of the paper, and that they have approved the final version.

15. Hu B, Yang XR, Xu Y, et al. Systemic immune-inflammation index predicts prognosis of patients after curative resection for hepatocellular carcinoma. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2014 Dec 1;20(23):6212-22.
16. Geng Y, Shao Y, Zhu D, et al. Systemic Immune-Inflammation Index Predicts Prognosis of Patients with Esophageal Squamous Cell Carcinoma: A Propensity Score-matched Analysis. *Sci Rep.* 2016;6:39482.
17. Hong X, Cui B, Wang M, Yang Z, Wang L, Xu Q. Systemic Immune-inflammation Index, Based on Platelet Counts and Neutrophil-Lymphocyte Ratio, Is Useful for Predicting Prognosis in Small Cell Lung Cancer. *Tohoku J Exp Med.* 2015;236(4):297-304.
18. Zhang Z, Hu Q, Hu T. Association of Lymphocyte to Monocyte Ratio and Risk of in-Hospital Mortality in Patients with Cardiogenic Shock: A Propensity Score Matching Study. *Int J Gen Med.* 2021;14:4459-4468.
19. Kim JW, Jung JY, Suh CH, Kim HA. Systemic immune-inflammation index combined with ferritin can serve as a reliable assessment score for adult-onset Still's disease. *Clin Rheumatol.* 2021;40(2):661-668.
20. Wu J, Yan L, Chai K. Systemic immune-inflammation index is associated with disease activity in patients with ankylosing spondylitis. *J Clin Lab Anal.* 2021;35(9):e23964.

REFERENCES

1. Dawson J, Linsell L, Zondervan K, et al. Epidemiology of hip and knee pain and its impact on overall health status in older adults. *Rheumatology (Oxford).* 2004;43(4):497-504.
2. EUMUSC. Musculoskeletal Health in Europe 2011; [Consulted 2014 Jan 08]; Disponible em: <http://www.eumusc.net/myUploadData/files/Musculoskeletal%20Health%20in%20Europe%20Report%20v5.pdf>.
3. Andrianakos AA, Kontelis LK, Karamitsos DG, et al. Prevalence of symptomatic knee, hand, and hip osteoarthritis in Greece. The ESORDIG study. *J Rheumatol.* 2006;33:2507-13.
4. Zhang W, Nuki G, Moskowitz RW, et al. OARSI recommendations for the management of hip and knee osteoarthritis: part III: Changes in evidence following systematic cumulative update of research published through January 2009. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage.* 2010;18:476-99.
5. Peat G, Thomas E, Duncan R, et al. Clinical classification criteria for knee osteoarthritis: performance in the general population and primary care. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2006;65:1363-7.
6. Bozic KJ, Kurtz SM, Lau E, et al. The epidemiology of revision total knee arthroplasty in the United States. *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 2010;468(1):45-51.
7. Miller J. Improved fixation in total hip arthroplasty using L.V.C. surgical technique (brochure). Warsaw, IN: Zimmer; 1980.
8. Li S, Scuderi G, Furman BD, et al. Assessment of backside wear from the analysis of 55 retrieved tibial inserts. *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 2002;404:75-82.
9. Jiranek WA, Machado M, Jasty M, et al. Production of cytokines around loosened cemented acetabular components. *J Bone Joint Surg* 1993;75-A(6):863-79.
10. Chiba J, Rubash HE, Rim KJ, et al.: The characterization of cytokines in the interface tissue obtained from failed cement less total hip arthroplasty with and without femoral osteolysis. *Clin Orthop* 1994;300:304-12.
11. Shanbly AS, Jacobs JJ, Black J, et al. Cellular mediators secreted by interfacial membranes obtained at revision total hip arthroplasty. *J Arthroplasty* 1995;10(4):498-506.
12. Spector TD, Hart DJ, Nandra D, et al. Low-level increases in serum C-reactive protein are present in early osteoarthritis of the knee and predict progressive disease. *Arthritis Rheum* 1997;40:723e7.
13. Livshits G, Zhai G, Hart DJ, et al. Interleukin-6 is a significant predictor of radiographic knee osteoarthritis: the Chingford study. *Arthritis Rheum* 2009;60:2037e45.
14. Luo H, He L, Zhang G, et al. Normal Reference Intervals of Neutrophil-To-Lymphocyte Ratio, Platelet-To-Lymphocyte Ratio, Lymphocyte-To-Monocyte Ratio, and Systemic Immune Inflammation Index in Healthy Adults: a Large Multi-Center Study from Western China. *Clin Lab.* 2019;65(3):10.7754/Clin.Lab.2018.180715.